

Original article

Serum zinc and selenium levels among severely malnourished and well-nourished under-five children in Maiduguri, north-eastern Nigeria

Lawan M. Bukar,^{1,2} Mohammed A. Alhaji,^{1,2} Halima A. Ibrahim,^{1,2} Hassan A. Elechi,^{1,2} Rebecca M. Gali,³ Abubakar G. Farouk,^{1,2} Jose P. Ambe.^{1,2}

¹Department of Paediatrics, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, College of Medical Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.

²Department of Paediatrics, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Nigeria.

³Department of Chemical Pathology, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, College of Medical Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.

***Corresponding author:** Prof. Abubakar Garba Farouk. Department of Paediatrics, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, College of Medical Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria. Tel No: +2348038164110. Email: farouk649@unimaid.edu.ng

Abstract

Background: Malnutrition, encompassing protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) and micronutrient deficiencies, is a major public health problem in many developing countries, including Nigeria. It is a significant risk factor for morbidity and mortality among children under five years of age. The study aimed to compare serum zinc and selenium levels between severely malnourished and well-nourished children under five years in Maiduguri, North-Eastern Nigeria. **Materials and methods:** A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted at the Paediatric wards and clinics of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) and State Specialist Hospital (SSH), Maiduguri, over 37 months (December 2016 – December 2019). A total of 190 children (100 severely malnourished, 90 well-nourished) aged 3–49 months were recruited using systematic random sampling. Serum zinc and selenium were assayed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS). Ethical clearance was obtained from both institutions. **Results:** The mean \pm SD serum zinc level for severely malnourished children was 0.04 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, compared to 0.06 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for well-nourished controls ($p < 0.01$). The mean \pm SD serum selenium level was 0.85 ± 0.34 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for severely malnourished children and 1.43 ± 0.46 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for well-nourished controls ($p < 0.01$). A positive correlation was observed between serum selenium and age, but not between serum zinc and age. No significant differences in zinc or selenium levels were found between the oedematous and non-oedematous forms of severe malnutrition. **Conclusion:** Severely malnourished under-five children in Maiduguri have significantly lower serum zinc and selenium levels compared to their well-nourished counterparts. The findings support integrating micronutrient Serum zinc;t assessment into the management of severe acute malnutrition, consistent with existing WHO protocols.

Keywords: Maiduguri, Serum selenium, Severe malnutrition, Well-nourished children.

Open Access article distribution in the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC by 4.0)

Copyright: The Author(s). 2025

ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20670002>

Date Submitted: 2nd March 2026

Date Accepted: 22nd April 2026

Date Published Online: 12th June 2026

Cite this article as: Lawan M. Bukar, Mohammed A. Alhaji, Halima A. Ibrahim, Hassan A. Elechi, Rebecca M. Gali, Abubakar G. Farouk, Jose P. Ambe. Serum Zinc and Selenium Levels among Severely Malnourished and Well-Nourished Under-Five Children in Maiduguri, North-Eastern Nigeria. *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; 2 (1): 319-324.

Introduction

Childhood malnutrition is a persistent global health challenge, particularly in developing countries.¹ The World Health Organisation (WHO) identifies it as the single most important risk factor for childhood morbidity and mortality in these settings.² Nigeria ranks among the top fifteen nations with the greatest burden of malnutrition and bears a high under-five mortality rate, to which malnutrition contributes significantly.^{3,4} Protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) predominantly affects children under five years due to their high nutritional demands, often in the context of poor weaning practices and recurrent infections.⁵

Beyond macronutrients, there is growing recognition of the critical role of micronutrients in child health. Deficiencies in trace elements such as zinc and selenium, often termed “hidden hunger,” can occur even without overt clinical signs and profoundly affect immune function, growth, and antioxidant defence.^{6,7} Zinc is a cofactor for numerous enzymes, essential for cellular growth and immunity.⁷ Selenium, a component of selenoproteins like glutathione peroxidase, is vital for protecting cells from oxidative damage.⁸ It is well-established that children with PEM frequently have concurrent deficiencies of these essential micronutrients, which can exacerbate their clinical vulnerability and complicate recovery.⁹

Maiduguri, in the semi-arid zone of North-Eastern Nigeria, has documented low soil zinc levels, which may affect the dietary intake of the local population.¹⁰ However, data on the serum levels of these critical trace elements in malnourished children in this region are limited. This study was therefore designed to compare serum zinc and selenium levels between severely malnourished and well-nourished under-five children in Maiduguri, providing local evidence to inform nutritional rehabilitation protocols.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This was a comparative cross-sectional study conducted at the Paediatric departments of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) and the State Specialist Hospital (SSH), Maiduguri. The study period was 37 months, from December 2016 to December 2019.

Study Population:

- **Cases:** Children aged 3 to 49 months with severe acute malnutrition (SAM), defined by the presence of bilateral pitting oedema (kwashiorkor) or severe wasting (marasmus, weight-for-height/length Z-score < -3 SD, or mid-upper arm circumference < 115 mm), as per WHO criteria.
- **Controls:** Apparently well-nourished children in the same age range, recruited from those attending the clinics for minor, non-debilitating illnesses or admitted for minor elective surgeries (e.g., herniotomy). Controls were frequency-matched to cases by age group and sex.

Exclusion Criteria: Children with known chronic diseases (e.g., congenital heart disease, cerebral palsy, sickle cell disease, tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS), those who had received zinc or selenium supplements within the preceding four weeks, or

those whose caregivers did not consent were excluded.

Sample Size and Sampling: A minimum sample size of 87 per group was calculated to detect a mean difference of 15 µg/dL in serum zinc, with a standard deviation of 30 µg/dL, at 80% power and a 5% significance level. Allowing for potential data loss, we aimed to recruit 100 cases and 90 controls. Systematic random sampling was used, recruiting every fifth eligible child who presented to the study sites after the study began, until the required sample size was reached.

Data and Specimen Collection: After obtaining written informed consent, a structured pro forma was used to record socio-demographic data and clinical findings. Socioeconomic status was assessed using the Oyediji classification, which stratifies families into five classes (I to V) based on parental occupation and education, with classes IV and V representing low socioeconomic status.¹¹ Weight was measured using a bassinet weighing scale for children <24 months and a stadiometer with a built-in scale for older children. Five millilitres of venous blood were collected aseptically into trace-element-free lithium heparin tubes. Samples were centrifuged within 2 hours, and serum was separated and stored at -20°C until analysis. Haemolysed samples were discarded.

Laboratory Analysis: Serum zinc and selenium concentrations were determined using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS Model 240FS, Agilent Technologies, USA) following standard operational procedures. Results were expressed in micrograms per millilitre (µg/mL). The laboratory reference ranges established for the local population were 0.65–1.10 µg/mL for zinc and 0.60–1.20 µg/mL for selenium.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed using SPSS version 18.0. Continuous variables were summarised as means and standard deviations, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. The Student’s t-test was used to compare means between groups, while the Chi-square (χ^2) test was used for categorical variables. Pearson’s correlation coefficient was used to assess the relationship between age and trace element levels. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Approval: Ethical clearance was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committees of both UMTH and SSH, Maiduguri.

Results

A total of 190 children (100 cases, 90 controls) were studied. The age of participants ranged from 3 to 49

months, with a mean of 16.9 ± 8.5 months for both groups combined. Over 77% of the children were under 24 months of age (Table 1).

Table 1: Age Distribution of the Study Population

Age group (months)	Cases n (%)	Controls n (%)
< 12	29 (29.0)	30 (33.3)
12 - 23	48 (48.0)	40 (44.4)
24 - 35	17 (17.0)	16 (17.9)
36 - 49	6 (6.0)	4 (4.4)
Total	100 (100)	90 (100)

The male-to-female ratio was approximately 1:1.2, with no significant difference between the groups ($\chi^2 = 0.05$, $p = 0.82$). The majority of participants (over 72%) belonged to the low socioeconomic classes (Oyedemi IV and V) (Table 2).

The mean serum zinc level was significantly lower in severely malnourished children (0.04 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) than in well-nourished controls (0.06 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, $p < 0.01$). This pattern was consistent across all age groups (Table 3). Similarly, the mean serum selenium level was significantly lower in malnourished children (0.85 ± 0.34 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) than in controls (1.43 ± 0.46 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$; $p < 0.01$). No significant differences in zinc or selenium levels were observed between children with oedematous malnutrition (kwashiorkor) and those with severe wasting (marasmus) (Table 4). There was a significant positive correlation between age and serum selenium level ($r = 0.24$, $p = 0.001$) but not between age and serum zinc level.

Table 2: Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Parameter	Cases n (%)	Controls n (%)	χ^2	p-value
Gender				
Male	47 (47.0)	42 (46.7)	0.05	0.82
Female	53 (53.0)	48 (53.3)		
Socio-economic Class				
High (I & II)	11 (11.1)	12 (12.8)	1.38	0.50
Middle (III)	13 (12.8)	16 (17.9)		
Low (IV & V)	76 (76.1)	62 (69.3)		

Table 3: Mean Serum Zinc Levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) by Age Group

Age group (months)	Cases Mean \pm SD	Controls Mean \pm SD	t-value	p-value
< 12	0.03 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.09	-4.02	< 0.01
12 - 23	0.04 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	-23.74	< 0.01
24 - 35	0.04 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	-11.56	< 0.01
36 - 49	0.04 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	-8.33	< 0.01

Table 4: Mean Serum Zinc and Selenium Levels by Type of Severe PEM

Micronutrient	Oedematous PEM Mean \pm SD	Severe Wasting Mean \pm SD	t-value	p-value
Zinc ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.04 \pm 0.01	0.04 \pm 0.03	-0.33	0.74
Selenium ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.83 \pm 0.30	0.85 \pm 0.38	-1.72	0.09

Figure 1. Correlation between Serum Selenium Level in $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for all 190 participants and Age in the Study Population

Discussion

This study confirms that severely malnourished children in Maiduguri have significantly lower serum zinc and selenium levels compared to their well-nourished peers. This coexistence of multiple micronutrient deficiencies in SAM is well established and underscores the need for comprehensive nutritional rehabilitation beyond macronutrient repletion.⁹

The finding of significantly lower serum zinc in malnourished children is consistent with reports from other Nigerian studies, such as those by Ugwuja et al. in Jos¹² and Abubakar *et al.*, in Kano,¹³ as well as studies from other developing countries.^{14,15} Notably, the zinc levels in our well-nourished control group were also lower than the standard reference range, a finding that mirrors reports of widespread zinc deficiency in rural communities in Edo State, Nigeria.¹⁶ This is likely attributable to the low zinc content of the soil in the semi-arid region of North-Eastern Nigeria, which directly impacts dietary intake.¹⁰ This observation highlights a broader public health issue of subclinical zinc deficiency, which our study design

does not fully capture but which has important implications for child health policy.

The finding of lower serum selenium levels in SAM is consistent with some international studies.¹⁷ However, we also observed that the absolute selenium levels in our study population were higher than some reference ranges, a phenomenon that requires careful interpretation. While we took strict precautions against pre-analytical contamination and used trace-element-free tubes, we cannot entirely rule out matrix interference during the AAS assay as a contributing factor. Importantly, our primary objective was a comparative analysis, and the significant *difference* between cases and controls remains valid, irrespective of the absolute population levels. The positive correlation of selenium with age may be related to cumulative dietary exposure and the introduction of more varied foods post-weaning, a finding consistent with Muntau et al.'s work in German children.¹⁸ The lack of difference in micronutrient levels between oedematous and non-oedematous forms of PEM in our cohort may reflect a shared underlying dietary deficiency in this setting.

Our study has limitations. The cross-sectional design prevents any inference on causality. The unexpectedly high serum selenium levels in both groups, while not invalidating the inter-group comparison, warrant confirmatory studies using a different assay method, such as inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), which is less susceptible to matrix effects. Furthermore, we did not concurrently measure markers of infection (e.g., C-reactive protein), which is a significant confounder in micronutrient assessment, as inflammation can depress serum zinc levels.

Conclusion

Severely malnourished under-five children in Maiduguri have significantly lower serum zinc and selenium levels than well-nourished children. The study population also appears to have a high background prevalence of zinc deficiency. The routine therapeutic feeds (F-75, F-100, RUTF) used in WHO protocols for managing severe acute malnutrition already contain zinc. Therefore, rather than recommending blanket high-dose supplementation, we recommend strict adherence to these existing WHO treatment protocols and the continued monitoring of micronutrient status in at-risk populations. Future research should investigate the bioavailability of these nutrients from local food sources and the potential clinical impact of this combined zinc-selenium deficiency on recovery from malnutrition.

Acknowledgements

Our sincere appreciation goes to Prof. M.B. Omotara, Prof. H Yusuph, Prof. W.A. Olowu, Prof M. Bello, Prof. MG Mustapha, Dr MG Ashir, Mallam Bashir Musa and staff of Department of Paediatrics UMTH for their numerous contributions to the completion of this research.

Conflicts of Interest:

None

Funding:

None.

References

1. Heiken GT, Manary M. 75 years of Kwashiorkor in Africa. *Malawi Med J.* 2009; 21: 96-100.
2. World Health Organisation. *Guideline: Updates on the management of severe acute malnutrition in infants and children.* Geneva: WHO; 2013.
3. UNICEF. *The State of the World's Children 2005.* New York: United Nations Children's Fund; 2005.
4. UNICEF. *The State of the World's Children 2011.* New York: United Nations Children's Fund; 2011.
5. Ulasi TO, Ebenebe J. Nutritional disorders in children. In: Azubuike JC, Nkanginieme KE, eds. *Paediatrics and Child Health in a Tropical Region.* 2nd ed. Owerri: African Educational Services; 2007: 250-9.
6. Shenkin A. Micronutrients in health and disease. *Postgrad Med J.* 2006; 82: 559-67.
7. Larry AG. Micronutrient mineral deficiencies. In: Kliegman RM, *et al.*, eds. *Nelson Textbook of Paediatrics.* 18th ed. Philadelphia: Saunders Elsevier; 2007: 265-7.
8. Rayman MP. Selenium and human health. *Lancet.* 2012; 379: 1256-68.
9. Bhutta ZA, Berkley JA, Bandsma RHJ, *et al.*, Severe childhood malnutrition. *Nat Rev Dis Primers.* 2017; 3: 17067.
10. Sodipo OA, AbdulRahman FI, Akan JC. Comparative elemental analysis of solanum macrocarpum (L) and soil sample from Alau, Borno state, Nigeria. *J Res Environ Sci Toxicol.* 2012; 1: 36-40.
11. Oyedeji GA. Socio-economic and cultural background of hospitalized children in Ilesha. *Nig J Paediatr.* 1985; 12(4): 111-7.
12. Ugwuja EI, Nwosu KO, Ugwu NC, Okonji M. Serum zinc and copper levels in malnourished preschool age children in Jos, Nigeria. *Pakistan J Nutr.* 2007; 6: 349-54.
13. Abubakar N, Atiku MK, Alhassan AJ, *et al.*, An assessment of micronutrients deficiency: A comparative study of children with PEM and apparently healthy controls in Kano, Northern Nigeria. *Trop J Med Res.* 2017; 20: 61-5.
14. Khubchandani A, Sanghani H, Sidhu G, *et al.*, Serum copper and zinc levels in preschool children with protein energy malnutrition. *Int J Res Med.* 2013; 2: 7-10.
15. Arnand J, Richard MJ, Favier A. Trace elements and protein calorie malnutrition in the Fes area (Morocco). *Biomed Pharmacother.* 1997; 51: 349-51.
16. Ibeawuchi ANE, Onyiriuka AN, Abiodun PO. Zinc nutritional status and anthropometric indices of preschool children living in a rural community in Edo state, Nigeria. *Pac J Med Sci.* 2017; 17: 10-21.

17. Salih MAM, Mohamed EH, Golgan V, *et al.*, Selenium in malnourished Sudanese children: status and interaction with clinical features. *Ann Nutr Metab.* 1994; 38: 68-74.
18. Muntau AC, Streiter M, Kappler M, *et al.*, Age-related reference values for serum selenium concentration in infants and children. *Clin Chem.* 2002; 48: 555-60.